

Writing from the Margin: An Analysis of Shashi Deshpande's That Long Silence

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Abstract

Shashi Deshpande is one of the more sensitive and versatile Indian woman writers in English. Popularly termed as a domestic novelist her novels and short stories explore the psyche of the middle-class educated Indian women, focusing primarily on her dilemma at being caught between modernity which implies freedom, individuality and self-expression and the patriarchal and traditional values that continue to permeate contemporary Indian society. Deshpande has created authentic female characters with recognizable credentials. She has successfully delineated their problems and plights, yearnings and aspirations, failures and foibles, dreams and disillusionment. The female 'quest for identity' has been a pet theme for Deshpande's novels. Their identity is minimized in family and their separated identity is attached with their husbands and sons relatively. There are certain social taboos prevailing in the society that completely doom the identity of women. Shashi Deshpande through her novel 'That Long silence' show how women are marginalized by the patriarchal society and how women allow themselves to be victimized for making a sweet relationship in the family. This paper attempts to analyze how women search for their identities and struggle for their existence in a patriarchal framework.

Keywords: Patriarchal, Modernity, Freedom, Yearnings, Disillusionment, Identity, Taboos, Marginalized, Victimized

மலர்: 13

சிறப்பிதழ்: 1

மாதம்: ஜனவரி

வருடம்: 2026

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.18206137](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18206137)

Introduction

Women's writing has questioned the existing viewpoints, which are patriarchal, conventional and traditional. Indian fiction has been enriched by highly talented women novelists including Kamala Markandaya, Anita Desai, Nayanthara Saghal, Chithra Banerjee, Arundhati Roy, Shashi Deshpande and others. They have written of Indian women, their conflicts and predicaments against the background of contemporary India. Their chief contribution consists of their exploring the moral and psychic dilemmas of their women characters along with their efforts to cope with the challenges. This helps to achieve a new harmony of relationship with themselves and their surroundings.

Virginia Woolf balanced male self-realization with female abnegation. In her essay Professions, Woolf complained that women's social obligations hindered a writing career. Their lives gave them a different perspective but women were not fundamentally different from men in their psychological needs and outlooks. The snow balling feminist movement very much disagreed and argued that "Women's writing is expressed as a distinctive female consciousness which was

more discursive and conjunctive than its male counterpart”. (Bhatnagar 56) Such consciousness was radically different and had been adversely treated. Women had been made to feel that they are inferior by nature and though men paid lip-service to equality, they would resist its implementation. Some men might be sympathetic to women’s issues, but only women themselves knew what they felt and wanted.

A plethora of Indian women novelists made their debut in the 1990s, producing novels which revealed the true state of Indian society and its treatment of women. They write about the urban middle class stratum of society they know best. Women writers have grappled with complex issues such as sensuality, servility, subjugation and society. They have handled them with a sense of balance, never disregarding the Indian traditions. Their novels distinctively assume feminist significance for focusing on the inner mind of Indian women in the feministic perspective.

Writing from the Margin

Women are often ‘marginalized’, ‘repressed’ in a literary work. The role of women is restricted by her womanhood and therefore, the experiences of the muted female forming half of the society which was not reflected in literature”. (Mohan 33) But with the rise of feminism, women has become aware of the fact that her inferiority is not ordained in heaven that gender is neither natural nor immutable. Revolting against their marginalization they have started questioning the sexual politics and gender arrangement.

Shashi Deshpande born in 1988 has emerged in recent years as one of the more sensitive and versatile Indian women writers writing in English. Popularly termed as a domestic novelist, her novels and short stories explore the psyche of the middle-class educated Indian women, focusing primarily on her dilemma at being caught between modernity which implies freedom, individuality and self-expression. Deshpande advocates a balance between a realistic perception of the contemporary social situation in India and the fundamental idea of feminism that a women be recognized as an individual in her own right and not to be restricted to the stereotypical roles and images like daughter, wife and mother.

In her novel, ‘That Long Silence’, Deshpande writes about the narrator Jaya, an upper middle class house wife in Bombay, with two teenage children, who is forced to take stock of her life when her husband is suspected of fraud and they move to a small flat in a poorer locality. The novelist shows how the silence imposed on women is partly of their own making, through society and tradition have a hand. India’s tradition and philosophy have no place here. The only reference to the part is in Jaya’s realization that in Sanskrit drama, women did not speak Sanskrit. They were confined to prakrit, a less polished language, imposing a variety of silence on them. The heroine Jaya incapable of breaking away from the supportive yet stifling extended family. The narrow focus results in an intensity which is almost painful. All the other characters including Mohan, Jaya’s husband, are fully realized, though none of them are likeable.

Women occupy a central place in Deshpande’s novels. They face the fact of tossing between tradition and modernity. Her main concern is the urge to find oneself, to create space for oneself to grow on one’s own. Her novels generally center on the family relationship particularly the relationship between husband and wife and the latter’s dilemma and conflicts. Identity can be an integrating force that brings closer the various aspects of the individual, that writes individuals in community and establishes harmony between communities. The female quest for identity has been a pet theme for many women novelists. Shashi Deshpande has also been one of such writer and she makes an earnest effort to understand the inner dimension of the female characters. For her portrayal of the predicament of middle-class educated Indian-women, their inner conflict, quest for identity, issues pertaining to parent-child relationship, marriage and sex, their exploitation and

disillusionment, Deshpande has been called a 'feminist'. For Deshpande's characters, marriage is no longer a sacrament. In 'That Long Silent', the couple is compared to 'a pair of bullocks yoked together'. Jaya in 'That Long Silent' is painfully conscious of the fact that around her husband 'needs and desires' her life revolves. She ruminates, "we seemed to be left with nothing but our bodies." (25)

Shashi Deshpande 'Writing from the Margin' is an essay that brings to light the women who are marginalized. She says that gender is the important factor which affects human life. Men and women differ in their bodies, attitudes, emotional behavior and the ways of looking things. But they share the common destiny of all living creatures of birth, growth, survival and death. These ideas are expressed in the essay and it can be well applied to a feminist interpretation of the novel 'That Long silence', Deshpande states that from the term 'women writers' marginalization begins. She says that male texts are theories; whether the female texts are experiences. Since women are marginalized in the society, women writers are also marginalized. The novel 'That Long silence' is about the claustrophobic world of women. It is about the exploration of women's self, divorced from her roles, from her gender-confinement.

Shashi Deshpande says that women writers are doubly confined, acting both as women and writer. She also talks about deep hole imagery where through the tiny openings women view the outside world. For women, world is still inside the walls and only through imagination she can cross the walls. In 'That Long silence' Jaya says "I have seen things differently. As if I've put my head down and looked up the world from between my legs. The world not just upside down but different". (58) Deshpande says that she had broken the bonds not only of Jaya herself, but Jaya the writer. She says "I was breaking out of my own bonds". (193) Self-revelation is what Jaya has to reach and she does. There is plethora of ideas that are examined in it like the man-woman relationship, marriage, family relationship, marriage, motherhood etc.

Breaking Silences in 'That Long Silence'

In the context of literature related to women, silence is used as a metaphor for submission and lack of self-expression. Moreover, silence in the context of the Indian women is the most important characteristic function of the code of conduct. It symbolizes the women's state in history and her conformity to tradition. Tradition has taught the Indian women to have a muted existence. She is taught to be timid and tolerant. She is taught never to raise her voice and her relationship is that of giving and sacrificing. Her conduct with her mother and other female members of the family is of silent assistance.

'Silence' in the context of this paper implies the suppression of women by denying them the right to express their feelings. It also implies the traditional expectation that the women will silently fall into the role strait-jacketed for them. Jaya, the protagonist in the novel 'That Long silence' is marginalized and she wears a kind of mask and disguises her role in different manner. A silent victimization is seen in the life of Jaya. A long silent journey in Jaya's life is a kind of marginalization that becomes an exploration of her life, divorced from her roles from her gender-confinement.

"The heroines of Shashi Deshpande's novels grow up surrounded by women who mostly endures the injustice done to them or resign to life of hopeless despair".(Pandey 62) Educated and intelligent, her protagonist refuse to submit or resign to an unquestioning life. 'That Long silence' is the most powerful portrayal of silence in a woman's life. Mohan's belief that "anger makes a woman 'unwomanly' teaches Jaya to control her anger. With this begins the process of learning her thoughts, feelings and needs unexpressed. Jaya is gradually trapped in a vicious cycle that engulfs her. She is made to accept silence which usurps her freedom to speak, her self-confidence and eventually her identity.

The life of Kusum in ‘That Long silence’ whose aim was to become ideal self-effacing women. Trying to achieve it she often emphasized her femaleness with exaggerated modesty. The way she pressurized herself into pleasing people and her failure to do so, proved to be a great setback for her. Her unthinking silence results in her madness. She inflicts herself with torturous silence, which increases her fear of being abandoned by her family and succumbing to it she jumps into a dried well to end her life. Nayana, the sweeper in ‘That Long silence’ continues to get pregnant in the hope of giving birth to a male child. In her unthinking silence, she gives in to her husband’s demand for a son, even though she truly loved her daughters and was happy to have them. The unthinking silence adopted as a part of life is also revealed through Mohan’s sister, Vimala in ‘That Long silence’ portrays her childlessness and makes her silently listen to her mother-in-law’s taunt. Her suffering that results from an “ovarian tumor with metastases” (39) because of which she bleeds to death, never finds a voice. She silently endures the pain and resigns to death without giving herself a chance to live.

Jaya’s maidservant, Jeeja too surrenders to unthinking silence, which help her to go on living. Married to a man who turns drunkard and batters her for money, Jeeja accepts all this brutality with a stoic silence and single mindedly goes on living. Jaya’s Saptagiri Ajji, also lives a life of unthinking silence. Strictly adhering to the traditional code of a conduct of a widow, she had chosen a life of severe abstinence from comforts and luxuries. Jaya’s neighbor in the Dadar flat, Mukta also maintains a stoic silence. After her husband, Arun who is killed in a train accident, Mukta devotes her life in maintaining harmony between her sharp-tongued mother-in-law and her rebellious children Nilima and Satish. Her own self has no importance and she never expresses her loneliness and frustration.

Conclusion

The fiction of Shashi Deshpande is distinctively post-colonial in the sense of a proud assertion of Indianness. Her protagonists are often educated women who struggle and break out of the family mould to choose their own life style, a feature that has become the norm in urban India. Her novels offer a vivid perception of the inner world of Indian womanhood. Deshpande’s novels usually begin with an unconventional marriage leading to the problems of alienation, accommodation and adjustment. The conflict in her protagonists is resolved through their desperate unconscious submission to traditional roles.

The term ‘New Woman’ has come to signify the awakening of woman into a new realization of her place and position in family and society, conscious of her individuality. The New woman has been trying to assert and ascertain her rights as a human being and is determined to fight for equal treatment with men. Ellen E. Jordan observes that “the English feminists endowed the ‘New Woman’ with her hostility to men, her questioning of marriage, her determination to escape from the restrictions of home life and her belief that education could make a woman capable of leading a financially self sufficient single and yet fulfilling life”. (Ellen. P.19)

A close study of Deshpande’s novels reveals her deep insight into the plight of Indian women who feel smothered and fettered in a tradition-bound male-dominated society. Her characters grapple with their struggle which drags them through innocence and experience, repression and submission, joy and sorrow that lends her novels an elemental sweep. Self realization is a vital term where the women characters of Deshpande have form within. “‘That Long silence’ is Jaya’s novel and the telling, the writing of it in itself the achievement, it is the final resolution. Self-revelation is what she has to reach and she does”. (Mohan 49) and yet as Jaya herself says, ‘self-revelation is a cruel process’. (89)

Shashi Deshpande through her novels and essays shows how women are marginalized by the patriarchal society and how women allow themselves to be victimized for making a sweet relationship in the family. Even though they face lot of trivial and consumptions, they come out of their bondage in the end. They break their silences and they are newly born.

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